

THE ROLE OF DEMONSTRATION WEAPONS IN PRIMARY CLASS SCIENCE TEACHING

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Abstract: *By teaching natural sciences in elementary school, students get information about nature, its objects, phenomena. The teacher uses demonstrations to introduce new concepts to the students during the lesson and organize the lesson effectively.*

Keywords— Nature, demonstrative weapons, live nature corner, room plants, map and globe, diafilm and movies.

INTRODUCTION

Students the first from class starting from nature and nature with depends without work activities excursions and subject in classes and reading from the book natural science in the content articles and " natural science" textbook reading in the process directly observations the way with they learn It's in training of students thinking activities organize to do help giver each different from equipment and first of all demonstrative of weapons is used .

Demonstrative to weapons natural or real objects and their picture, picture, diagram enters in teaching slide film and movies, TV shows and of teaching another technique tools more and more wide is being used. Har which demonstrative weapons certain the goal looking forward to is used.

Natural weapons are nature are bodies. They are about the studied material much real imaginations will give and in children directly acceptance to do based on nature about concepts harvest to be possibility will give.

That's it according to in class or natural science in his room live nature learning for each different room plants as well own of places trees for special has been branches , leaves , flowers , fruit and seeds to be necessary In natural science classes live nature in the corner being cultivated from plants , as well as herbarium and from the excursion take bride from plants is used . Nature in learning held lessons on time and on excursions natural conditions live nature from objects is used .

Also natural of objects animals also use in learning ok Although many animals to the children in class (live nature in the corner) display possible to excursions though separately attention to give need will be because in this students only their external appearance just to see not but characteristic actions and behaviors with get to know opportunity have will be Alive animals when not their chuchelalari (tulums), mulajlari or photos and from pictures use can However they are about alive animals natural in the circumstances pointer motion pictures much more difficult imaginations will give .

Lifeless nature also natural in learning from weapons , for example , every different in color granite , mica , quartz , field spar , clay , sand , calcite (boron , marble , limestone), salt (

fertilization for), rock salt and potassium salt , har different coal , iron , copper of ores samples as well metals and alloys (iron , cast iron , steel , aluminum) , soil samples and others to be need

In children directly acceptance to do possible didn't happen nature bodies and events about sure and right imaginations harvest to do for displayed of weapons is used .

In grades 1-4 students for question and assignments which was "Observations from his diary use necessary ". Observations diary with students only only in class not but they also work at home . In his diaries regularly records to the students own their observations analysis to do , nature events between reason connections , as well as nature and people of labor mutually connection to determine help will give .

Map and globe . Students through natural science map and globe about initial imaginations that 's why for in class Uzbekistan Republic of natural map , half balls natural map , natural zones map is useful fossils map to be need Also surroundings place conditional to the signs have has been big scalable plan and students living and is studying city or population to live of places plan is also used .

In class diameter 42.5 cm big from the globe , in individual work while diameter From a 15 cm globe is used .

Projection devices . Projection to devices in a bottle slides demonstration who does projection lamp , clear on the curtain slides demonstration who does cadoscope and filmscopes enters In class slides demonstration from doing before teacher manual content with get to know and there is devices with work styles practical respectively occupied to be need

natural science classes an overhead projector is also used in it factory method done clear on the curtain drawn special transporters and also do not weapons (color schemes), pictures , sections from the side appearances and another weapons is used .

Transporter that's it with conveniently , it's every different processes (eg lake grass clicks , resources , that is springs harvest to be , in nature the water circle across rotation etc.) show in dynamics (in action) . enable will give . Such to the effect transporter personnel consistency with put to go with is achieved . Overhead projector directly hardware on the table

usual felt-tip pen , ballpoint pen pen or pencil with clear on the curtain drawn each how picture , scheme side view on the screen to show possibility will give .

Screen tools (diafilms , slides , slides) are the main ones place or main filler as helper place perform can Screen weapons mural pictures such as to necessity looking demonstration will be done . One of the lesson from 5-6 frames use recommendation will be done . Some 10 cases from personnel if used will be They are documentary , visible or multiplied to be can Of them to the goal directed without use necessary Screen of weapons personnel attention with to see should , but long time not because in this film and mirror hot goes and shape change or cracked leaving can From this except light photo strong impressive as to see organ quickly it's tiring and therefore too quickly for of students to boredom reason will be Complicated from personnel of use the most a lot time is 1-2 minutes . If the lesson purpose those that have passed repetition if , then light the number of pictures (frames) is up to 20-25 be multiplied can

Remember catch should be shown the photo of students themselves explanations need Only student what they saw wrong while explaining, from the topic except the important ones only when he doesn't see it of the teacher intervention road is placed.

CONCLUSION

Experiments transfer for equipment. Experiments and laboratory training for (in classes and young naturalists in the circle) special equipment : measure tools , magnifying glass , laboratory equipment , utensils , materials , assistant tools need Measurement tools each different of liquids certain size measure for beakers , thermometers and that's it etc enters Some tools of students themselves preparations can Laboratory equipment laboratory tripods , tripods , alcohol lamps , asbestos net , test tube to put tripods , clamps , as well containers (test tubes , glass funnels , flasks), white glass vials , containers set - tea glasses , light bulbs and others enters.

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